

www.arseam.com

STATUS OF HIGHER EDUCATION FACULTY IN INDIA: A REVIEW

Prof. (Dr.) Ritu Gandhi Arora

DAV Institute of Management
Faridabad, Haryana India,

Abstract

India is a developing country and have recognised as a pool of talented human resources by the world as a whole. It has highly qualified and educated workforce, which is known to be an essential factor for economic development. It is a fact that human efforts, competence, skill and aptitude contribute to economic growth by fully utilising productive resources and adopting and prompting advance technology. The best education infrastructure and faculty produces well educated labour force by enhancing both quantity and quality of education. Today India is attempting to build a knowledge society with the assumption that knowledge and competitive skills of workforce can be built only by focussing on higher and technical education. As a result, in the last few years lot of attention has been paid towards the quality and excellence in higher education.

The attractiveness and potential of higher education in India is a result of major proportion of our population, which is between the age group of 18-23 years and globalisation of the Indian economy. Quality education is the key to growth and the theory of economic growth has concentrated much on the role of education which ultimately affects the future of the country. The present study is an attempt to review the present status and the need of the higher education faculty of our country. The review also gives an insight to the need of motivated faculty for higher education.

Key words: Higher Education, Faculty, Globalisation, Quality, Economic Growth.

Introduction

Indian Higher Education is a rising sector for investment in the recent past. It is one of the major contributors to the GDP of Indian economy. The higher education scenario in India shows that a number of central, state, deemed and private universities are entering into the education sector.

Growth of this sector can be attributed to low literacy rate, higher urban concentration and rising per capita income. The government is also facilitating the growth of this sector by giving various grants and facilities to the researchers and budding entrepreneurs. The focus of the economy towards building human capital has also contributed towards the rise of this sector through the introduction of skill development program.

In making higher education sector a success the major role player is faculty involved in higher education. The quality and potential of higher education faculty will influence the quality of workforce available in the future. About 150mn population is in the 18-23years age group (ESG, MHRD, 2014), showing the level of responsibility on higher education institutions and ultimately on higher education faculty.

The responsibilities of institution and faculty cannot be ignored. From the present status of universities it can be concluded that the faculty members are less than what is mandatory, or the faculty is of poor quality. Indian education system is under the influence of centralization, bureaucracy and lack of accountability, transparency, and professionalism. The number of affiliating colleges and the number of students have increased which has increased the administrative functions of the universities. This has resulted in less focus on academics and research activities.

Faculty shortages and the inability of the state educational system to attract and retain well-qualified teachers have been posing challenges to quality education for many years. The quality of teaching is also often poor and there are constraints faced in training the faculty as well. Hence the quality of education is deteriorating due to unavailability of trained faculty. The regulatory framework at central and state level is complex and not clear. This requires the severe need for enhancing the attractiveness of teaching as a profession.

The present study is an attempt to review these aspects of higher education faculty in India. It gives insight into the current scenario of higher education faculty in the universities as well as the other aspects which influence the performance of the faculty.

2. Indian Higher Education Sector

Indian Higher Education Sector can be divided into four broad categories:

Category I

Formal Education: It includes (i) Institutes of national importance (ii) Universities (iii) Colleges (iv) Polytechnics. These are regulated by UGC, State Government and IGNOU. National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is for the accreditation of the institutions which fall under this category. NAAC established by UGC in 1994.

Category II

Technical and Professional Education Institutes: It includes Engineering colleges, Management Schools, Law, Medical and Pharmacy colleges. These institutions are regulated by AICTE, Bar Council of India and Medical Council of India respectively. The accreditation of these institutions is done through National Board of Accreditation (NBA). NBA was setup by AICTE in 1994. For agricultural education accreditation is done by accreditation board set up by ICAR in 1996.

Category III

Skill Development: This category includes ITIs, ITCs, and Private Skill Development institutes. The regulatory body is DGET in case of ITIs/ITCs. There is no accreditation body for institutions under this category.

Category IV

Vocational Training: This includes Finishing schools, English training, Air hostess Academies. There is no regulatory and accreditation body for the institutions in this category also.

2.1. Indian Higher Education Institutions.

The higher education institutions have been classified in following 3 broad categories (ASIHE 2011-12 Page 2 of 11):

(a) University & University Level Institutions i.e. the Institutions which are empowered to award degree under some Act of Parliament (Central universities) or State Legislature (State Universities). Deemed Universities are institutions which have been accorded the status of a university with authority to award their own degrees through central government notification.

In India, "University" means a University established or incorporated by or under a Central Act, a Provincial Act or a State Act and includes any such institution as may, in consultation with the

University concerned, be recognised by the University Grants Commission (UGC) in accordance with the regulations made in this regard under the UGC Act, 1956.

(b) Colleges/Institutions which are not empowered to provide degree in its own name and therefore are affiliated/recognised with Universities. Institutes of National Importance (prestigious institutions awarded the said status by Parliament), and Institutions established by State Legislative Act and colleges affiliated with the University (both government-aided and unaided).

(c) Stand-Alone institutions (not affiliated with Universities) which are not empowered to provide degree and therefore run Diploma Level Programmes. These are, (i) Technical such as Polytechnics, Post Graduate Diploma in Management recognised by AICTE and administered by State Directorate of Technical Education, (ii) Teacher Training such as District Institute of Education & Training recognized by National Council for Teacher Education and administered by State Council for Education Research & Training and (iii) Nursing Institutes recognized by Indian Nursing Council and administered by State Nursing Council/Boards Institutions running diploma level programmes and directly regulated/administered by Central Ministries.

The nature of degree-awarding institutions in India is complicated primarily due to affiliation and funding sources. The Central Universities are fully funded by the central government, state universities are funded by state governments and occasionally assisted by the central government, Private state universities are funded by private individuals or trusts, Deemed universities are government or privately funded, and institutions of national importance are funded by the central government.

2.2. Present Statistics of Higher Education Institutions in India

When India got independence there were about 20 universities and 500 colleges whereas today there are 712 universities (42 central, 310 state public, 127 Deemed, 143 state private, 1 central open, 13 state open universities, 68 institutions established through state legislation, 5 institutions of national importance and 3 others) and 36671 colleges (ESG, MHRD, 2014). In the academic year 2012-13 the overall enrolment of students was 29.6 million (MHRD Report 2012-13). The responsibility of these universities, educational institutions have increased to large

extent due to growth of service sector and knowledge driven society. The focus now is to develop Human capital. The faculty in these universities and other educational institutions are now entrusted with the responsibility of developing Human Capital. Ensuring quality in higher education is amongst the foremost challenges being faced in India today, with few institutes having achieved global recognition for excellence.

2.3. Higher Education Faculty of India

India as a developing country is progressing towards economic and industrial development. This can be achieved through investment in human capital with focus on knowledge of the manpower. The focus of knowledge development is more on the higher education faculty as major workforce of India includes either faculty of Higher Education or students.

Universities are playing key role in spreading Higher Education in India and the key regulatory body of universities is UGC. It has laid down the guidelines for the higher education faculty, the career path of a faculty who joins a university as: Assistant Professor (AGP of Rs. 6000-7000) for 5 years, Assistant Professor (AGP Rs. 7000-8000) for 5 years, Associate Professor (Rs 8000-9000) for 3 years, Professor (Rs 9000-10000) for 10 years, and Professor (Rs 10000-12000).

Higher Education Faculty are entrusted with the responsibility to develop Human Capital. India is having highly qualified faculty serving in all the higher education institutions. However, the challenges faced by the higher education faculty cannot be ignored. There is a need to focus on these challenges in order to keep the faculty motivated and thus ensure quality teaching.

3. Challenges faced by higher education faculty in India

Higher Education Faculty is facing several challenges while serving to develop the employable human capital for the country. This section discusses the various challenges today's higher education faculty is facing.

3.1 More expectations from current faculty due to vacant faculty positions

Statistics show that there is a huge gap between the demand and supply. The prestigious institutes of higher education like IIT, IIM, IISc, NIT etc in the country are facing a severe faculty crunch. The institutes of higher learning under the Ministry of Human Resource Development (HRD) face a faculty shortage to an extent of 35% according to the latest government data.

TABLE 1: Faculty Shortage

Type of an Institute	Name	Faculty Strength (Sanctioned)	Faculty Strength (Current)	Vacant	Vacancy (%)
IITs	Indian Institute of Technology	6653	4079	2574	39%
IIITs	Indian Institute of Information Technology	253	162	91	36%
IIMs	Indian Institute of Management	766	577	189	25%
IISERs	Indian Institute of Science Education and Research	861	746	115	13%
SPAs	School of Planning and Architecture	672	618	54	8%
NITs	National Institute of Technology	6056	4292	1764	29%
CUs	Central Universities	16328	10058	6270	38%
	Total	31589	20532	11057	35%

(Data, as available with Ministry of HRD as on 25th November, 2014, includes Visiting, Adjunct & Contract Faculty also.)

As Table 1 shows, IITs top the list with 39% vacancies and Central Universities follow with 38% vacancies. One would assume that a large number of new institutions setup in the last few years and that their faculty numbers might be contributing to this overall number. But this assumption is not supported by numbers. The new IITs face only a 22% shortage while the old IITs face a much greater 41% faculty crunch. Some of the oldest institutions like IIT Roorke, IIT BHU have more than half their faculty positions vacant. IIT Bhubaneshwar has a shortage of only 4%.

Out of IIMs, IIM Indore is facing a 52% shortage while IIM Ranchi is facing a 48% shortage. IIM Udaipur & IIM Raipur are the only two IIMs with no shortage of faculty. The older IIMs at Ahmedabad, Calcutta & Bangalore are also facing a severe shortage of faculty. IIM Ahmedabad is the worst hit with a 29% shortage

Out of the NITs, 5 of them are facing a shortage of over 40%. NIT Delhi tops the list with 50% Shortage of faculty. The NITs in Raipur,

Uttarakhand & Meghalaya each are facing only 8% shortage of faculty. In terms of the overall numbers, NITs seem to be better placed than the IITs with 29% shortage of faculty. Out of all the institutes, the School of Planning & Architecture (SPAs) seem to be better placed in terms of faculty. They only have a shortage of 8%. Even in the Central Universities, it is the old universities that are worst hit. Delhi University has a shortage of more than 50% closely followed by University of Allahabad.

“The most acute weakness plaguing India’s higher education system is a crisis of governance. Its most visible manifestation is a crisis of faculty. The generation that was inspired by a broad commitment to the public good has retired or will do so soon. There is little likelihood of sufficient replenishment, given entrenched mediocrity in institutions with lifetime appointments, few competitive pressures and abysmal governance.”(Devesh Kapur & Pratap Bhanu Mehta).

The statistics related to the ratio of student to faculty also reveals that as compared to demand the supply of faculty is less.

Table 2: Less supply of Faculty through Student/Faculty ratio

Type	Name	Total No	Student Strength	Faculty Strength (Current)	Student/Faculty Ratio
IITs	Indian Institute of Technology	16	66002	4079	16:1
IIITs	Indian Institute of Information Technology	4	4776	162	29:1
IIMs	Indian Institute of Management	13	3489	577	6:1
IISERs	Indian Institute of Science Education and Research	6	6997	746	9:1
SPAs	School of Planning and Architecture	4	7162	618	12:1
NITs	National Institute of Technology	30	74810	4292	17:1

In terms of Student/Faculty ratio as shown in table 2, it is the IIMs that are doing best with one faculty for every 6 students. In the case of IITs, it is one faculty for every 16 students. IIITs have the worst ratio with one faculty for every 29 students. In NITs, there is one faculty for every 17 students.

From the above data the present Pupil Teacher Ratio (PTR) in higher education is around 1:23, the recommended value as per University Grants Commission guidelines is 1:12 for post graduate students and 1:15 for undergraduates. Even the international reputed institutions like IITs are having more than 30% faculty positions lying vacant.

3.2 Quality of Education and NAAC Accreditation

Another challenge which is being faced by faculty of higher education is the mandatory accreditation in higher education institutes which is shifting faculty focus on quality of education. NAAC is the accreditation body at the university level. Institutions under the regulation of AICTE are accredited through NBA. For accreditation faculty needs to focus on the aspects of teaching, developing themselves and students, focusing on research oriented activities. Accreditation is market driven and has an international focus. It assesses the characteristics of an Institution and its programmes against a set of criteria established by Board of Accreditation. Accreditation process quantifies the strengths, weaknesses in the processes adopted by the Institution and provides directions and opportunities for future growth. Accredited Institutions may be preferred by funding agencies for releasing grants for research as well as expansion etc. It signifies that the Institutional performance is based on assessment carried out through an independent competent body of quality assessors, with strengths and weaknesses emanating as a feedback for policymaking. Accreditation provides a quality seal or label that differentiates the Institutions from its peers at the national level. This leads to a widespread recognition and greater appreciation of the brand name of Institutions and motivates the Institutions to strive for more.

So the accreditation process motivates faculty to participate actively in academic and related Institutional / departmental activities. It helps to create sound and challenging academic environment in the Institution, and contributes to social and economic development of the country by producing high quality technical manpower.

3.3 Research Activities

UGC being the regulatory body at the university level has set the performance indicators for higher education faculty (Assistant Professors, Associate Professors and Professors). Under the research contribution it is been specified that as the faculty moves up in the career path the research activities increase. The faculty needs to engage in research activities like conducting research, working on research projects and publishing the research work. The involvement in research is a major indicator of performance of faculty hence for promotion; a faculty needs to

conduct research activities. Points related to research activities contributes a lot towards the minimum Academic Performance and Service Requirements for Direct Recruitment and CAS Promotion in Universities & Colleges.

Filing and getting Patents is also emerging as a necessary challenge before the faculty. The accreditation board (NAAC, NBA) assess the quality of the institution or of the faculty through the number of patents filed and received.

3.4. Focus on Self Development

The most challenging aspect today for faculty is to impart quality education along with their own development. UGC has made it mandatory, in the performance indicators that a faculty needs to undergo a certain minimum numbers of training programs in order to get promotion. For imparting such training and development programs to faculty, academic staff colleges are established by UGC. These staff colleges offer refresher, orientation, soft skill courses to faculty for their development.

Apart from the mandatory training requirements a faculty needs to learn the current teaching methodology, latest research techniques and methods. Continuous learning and development is required from the faculty.

3.5. Student related co-curricular, extension & field based activities

This includes extension work through NSS / NCC and other channels, cultural / technical activities, subject related events, advisement and counselling. For this a faculty needs to engage in Institutional Co-curricular activities for students such as field studies/educational tours/industrial tour/field training/quiz/contest/declamation contest, guidance & counselling etc.

A faculty needs to either lead or participate in Extension Work and National services like NSS, NCC, Red Cross, Eco-Club, women Cell. Along with these activities Community work such as values of National Integration, Environment democracy, social work, Human Rights, peace, scientific temper, flood or drought relief, small family norms, tree plantation, energy conservation, Library literacy programme, etc. through lectures/awareness programmes or through TV/Satellite/ EDUSAT/Radio etc. It is challenging for the faculty to conduct these

activities along with teaching and research activities. As mentioned in the UGC performance indicators, involvement in these activities is essential to get promotion.

3.6. Contribution to Corporate life and management of the department and institution through participation in academic and administrative committees:

A faculty needs to contribute to Corporate life in Universities/colleges through meetings, popular lectures, expert/extension lectures, EDUSAT lectures, INSPIRE programmes, invited lectures on subject related/scientific/legal etc. issues, or articles in college magazine and University volumes. Participation of the faculty in committees concerned with any aspect of departmental or institutional activity such as admission (including online admission), budget/purchase, time-table, campus development, inspection, library, students welfare, placement, help desk, anti-ragging, UMC etc.

4. Conclusion

The Indian higher education institutions are facing shortage of faculty. This shortage is increasing the expectations from the current faculty. The present faculty is unable to work efficiently due to complexities in regulatory agencies, funding institutions and less developed guidelines. The faculty is required to deliver quality education due to mandatory accreditation. Along with the teaching a faculty needs to perform several other activities related to the society and administration of the institution in which they are working. While performing these duties the faculty must not ignore the aspect that a major contribution is required through them in the field of research. All this needs to be done along with their self development through the faculty development programs.

The paper concludes that the higher education faculty in India are facing lots of challenges. These challenges will not only help in increasing the efficiency of the faculty but will also play a important role in building the human capital for the country.

5. References and Bibliography:

- [1]. All India Survey on Higher Education 2011-12, Government of India Ministry of Human Resource Development Department of Higher Education, New Delhi, 2013.
- [2]. Consolidated Working Group Report, for XII Five Year Plan on Higher Education, Administration, Deloitte Analysis, Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu India Private Limited (DTTIPL), 2012.
- [3]. Deepti Gupta & Navneet Gupta, Higher Education in India: Structure, Statistics and Challenges, Journal of Education and practice Vol 3, No 2, 2012.
- [4]. Devesh Kapur, Chapter: Indian Higher Education, National Bureau of Economic Research, Volume Title: American Universities in a Global Market, Volume Author/Editor: Charles T. Clotfelter, Volume Publisher: University of Chicago Press, Volume ISBN: 0-226-11044-3; 978-0-226-11044-8, May 2010
- [5]. Devesh Kapur & Pratap Bhanu Mehta, Indian Higher Education Reform: From Half-Baked Socialism to Half-Baked Capitalism, Presentation at Brookings-NCAER India Policy Forum 2007, New Delhi, July 17-18, 2007
- [6]. Educational Statistics at a glance, Government of India, Ministry of Human Resource Development Bureau of Planning, Monitoring & Statistics, New Delhi, 2014
- [7]. FICCI Report, Higher Education in India: Vision 2030. Summit 2013.
- [8]. Faculty norms prescribed by AICTE for various programs 2010.
- [9]. Unstarred Question Number 296, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Answered on 25-02-2015 in the Lok Sabha.

[10].UGC guidelines for minimum academic performance and service requirements for promotion of teachers in universities,2012.

Websites visited:

www.aicte-india.org

www.nbaind.org

www.mhrd.gov.in

www.ugc.ac.in

www.naac.gov.in